

Design and Localization Technique of a Winning Robot for Precision Donut Stacking Using YOLO and Rotational Angle Detection

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Abstract—This paper presents the design and implementation of a 1st place-winning robot developed for the INNOVEDEX Robotics Competition Thailand 2025. The competition tasked robots with autonomously detecting, picking, stacking, and placing color-coded donut-shaped objects in a prescribed order. The proposed robot features a vertically actuated end-effector mechanism that enables precise object pickup and release, minimizing positional error during stacking. Object detection is performed using the YOLO algorithm to identify both object class and color. To determine object location, a rotational angle-based localization approach is employed: the camera, mounted on the robot's arm, sweeps around the work area while tracking the object's centroid. The rotation angle at which the centroid aligns with a predefined radial line from the rotation axis is used to estimate the object's position. Detection robustness is further enhanced by tuning a pixel-based alignment tolerance parameter ($\pm n$ pixels). Experimental results in the competition environment demonstrate that the system achieves reliable detection and high placement accuracy under varying lighting and object positions, contributing to the team's first-place victory. The approach offers a practical and efficient solution for object localization in constrained competitive environments.

Keywords—stacking robot, YOLO, rotational angle-based localization

I. INTRODUCTION

In competitive robotics, it is common for teams to document and publish their robot designs so that others may use them as reference models and further improve upon them. For example, the RoboCup competitions have generated extensive technical literature describing hardware configurations, control strategies, and perception systems, enabling knowledge transfer across research groups [1]. Similarly, low-cost competition robot arms have been designed and detailed for public dissemination, providing valuable design guidelines for future implementations [2].

Robotics competitions such as INNOVEDEX provide a unique environment where engineering constraints, real-world uncertainty, and time-critical decision-making converge. Unlike industrial applications where robots operate in controlled settings, competition robots must perform reliably under strict rules, limited hardware budgets, and dynamically changing conditions such as random object placement and varying lighting. These challenges make competitions valuable testbeds for developing and validating novel robotic design approaches and vision-based perception techniques.

One of the recurring challenges in object manipulation tasks is achieving accurate detection and localization of objects with simple, low-cost hardware. Industrial solutions often rely on multiple high-resolution cameras, depth sensors, or external motion-capture systems; however, such solutions are prohibited in most competition rules, which often restrict teams to a single onboard camera. Under these constraints, robots must achieve real-time detection and precise localization using lightweight algorithms that can run efficiently on limited computing hardware.

In the context of the INNOVEDEX Robotics Competition Thailand 2025, robots were tasked with autonomously detecting, picking, and stacking color-coded donut-shaped objects in a prescribed order. Success in this challenge required not only robust detection of objects but also highly accurate placement during stacking, since misalignment could lead to task failure. To address this, our robot was designed with three key contributions:

1. A vertically actuated end-effector optimized for precision pickup and release, minimizing positional error during stacking.
2. A YOLO-based detection framework trained specifically for identifying the class and color of donut-shaped objects under varying lighting and positional conditions.
3. A rotational angle-based localization technique, in which the camera, mounted on the rotating robot arm, estimates object location by aligning detected centroids with a predefined radial line. This approach reduces the need for complex depth estimation while still achieving high placement accuracy.

By combining these elements, the proposed system demonstrates how competition constraints can be transformed into opportunities for innovation in robot design and vision-based localization. The results from the competition environment confirm that the approach not only enabled reliable task completion but also contributed to securing first place in the national contest.

Following this practice, this paper presents the design and implementation of our first-place-winning robot developed for the INNOVEDEX Robotics Competition Thailand 2025. The remaining sections are organized as follows: Section II outlines the competition rules and constraints. Section III details the robot design. Section IV describes the object detection system, while Section V explains the angular localization method. Section VI presents the experimental

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. CAD model (a) and corresponding 3D-printed SCARA-style robotic arm with integrated camera system (b).

IV. OBJECT DETECTION

YOLO (You Only Look Once) [3] was employed as the object detection framework to both localize doughnuts within the captured images and determine their center positions. Beyond localization, the model was trained to classify each doughnut according to its color category, enabling simultaneous detection and recognition. To prepare the training data, a large dataset of doughnut images was collected under varying backgrounds, orientations, and lighting conditions. Each image was manually annotated with bounding boxes and labeled by color, ensuring that the model could learn robust features for both spatial localization and color classification.

During training, the model optimized its ability to predict bounding boxes with high precision while assigning the correct color label. This dual-task learning allowed the system to operate reliably in real-time scenarios, even when doughnuts appeared at different scales or under non-uniform illumination. After training, the model achieved an accuracy of 100%, demonstrating consistent performance in detecting and classifying doughnuts within the competition setup.

As shown in Fig. 5, the robotic arm operating during the competition stage employs a mounted camera to capture images of the conveyor area, which are subsequently processed by the trained YOLO model. As illustrated in Fig. 6, the model produces bounding boxes and corresponding center points for each doughnut, which are then utilized to determine their precise spatial locations in order to facilitate accurate object localization and manipulation.

Fig. 5. Robotic arm in operation during the competition stage.

Fig. 6. YOLO detection output with bounding box and class label.

V. ANGULAR LOCATION DETECTION

The conveyor is designed as a semicircular strip with a width greater than the diameter of a doughnut. Consequently, doughnuts may rest near the inner edge, the midpoint, or the outer edge of the strip. Since the gripper is wide enough to span the conveyor, it can pick up a doughnut at any radial position without requiring radial adjustment. Thus, only the angular location of the doughnut relative to the robot arm base must be determined.

To obtain this angular location, a radial reference line is drawn on the image captured by the camera mounted on the robot arm, as illustrated in Fig. 7. The line extends from the arm base toward the conveyor edge. As the arm rotates from 0° (left) to 180° (right), the system determines the angle at which the radial line intersects the center of a detected doughnut. This intersection angle is then recorded as the doughnut's angular position.

The performance of this method is affected by two key parameters. First, the rotation speed of the robot arm determines whether YOLO can process the image in time before the line passes over the doughnut center; excessive speed can lead to missed detections. Second, the thickness of the radial line, defined as the alignment tolerance parameter, impacts the trade-off between detection rate and angular precision: a higher tolerance increases detection probability but reduces precision, while a lower tolerance achieves greater precision but may lower detection reliability.

By analyzing these two parameters—rotation speed and alignment tolerance—the system can be tuned for optimal performance, ensuring both fast and reliable angular location detection.

Fig. 7. YOLO output image with the blue angular detecting line.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a vision-based system for doughnut detection and localization in a robotic competition environment. A YOLO model was trained to detect doughnuts and classify their colors. The detected center points were then used to determine the angular location of doughnuts on a half-circular conveyor, enabling the robot arm to position its gripper correctly for successful pickup.

An angular detection method based on a radial line scan was introduced, with performance evaluated in terms of rotation speed and alignment tolerance. The study highlighted the trade-off between angular precision and detection reliability, providing a basis for tuning system parameters to achieve both fast and dependable operation.

Overall, the proposed approach demonstrates the feasibility of integrating real-time object detection with angular localization for efficient robotic manipulation. Future work may focus on further improving detection speed, enhancing robustness under varying lighting conditions, and

extending the method to objects of different shapes and sizes. To facilitate reproducibility, our source code and robot design files are publicly available at [4].

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